

Performance of a biochar produced from cellulose as admixture in constructed wetlands used to treat wastewater effluent and combined sewer overflows

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the purification capacity of different admixtures in Vertical Flow Constructed Wetlands (VFCWs) when simultaneously applied as a post-treatment to remove micropollutants (MPs) and to depurate untreated wastewater from Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs). The main novelty lies with the performance intensification of the mixing sand substrate with two alternatives of biologically activated biochar, that can increase the treatment efficiency and also its circularity. Preliminary results demonstrated the feasibility of cellulose recovery and subsequent application of produced biochar for MPs mitigation in the same catchment as the ideal closing loop, where 'waste' material is recovered and valorised at once.

Keywords

Biochar, cellulose, combined sewer overflow, constructed wetlands, micropollutants

INTRODUCTION

The growing focus on sustainability over the past decade stems from mounting environmental challenges like biodiversity loss, pollution, and resource depletion. Concurrently, socioeconomic issues like unemployment and inequality have led to the promotion of a Circular Economy (CE), which aims to better manage resources in a regenerative, closed-loop system aligned with the UN's 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) reduce urban emissions but wastewater also contains valuable components, such as cellulose, lipids, and volatile fatty acids, that can be recovered for biobased products like biochar, biodiesel, and bioplastics (Frkova et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2022). Cellulose, for instance, accounts for 4 million tons of toilet paper waste annually in the EU. While traditionally deposited or incinerated, cellulose fibers – accounting for up to 30% of the influent chemical oxygen demand (COD) - can be recovered and converted into biochar via slow pyrolysis. Activated biochar, conventionally created through physical or chemical treatments, has shown limited performance compared to commercial options for removing micropollutants (MPs) from wastewater, necessitating innovative approaches. Biological activation of biochar has emerged as a efficient and sustainable alternative to enhance pollutant removal in Constructed Wetlands (CWs), a cost-effective technology suited as post-treatment step for small-to-medium sized WWTPs (Venditti et al., 2022). Traditionally, efforts to minimize pollution have focused on WWTPs effluent discharges. However, recent attention has shifted to Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) which act as release valves in combined sewer systems, discharging directly into the environment to prevent overloading WWTPs and reduce the risk of overloading the drainage systems. CSO discharges can harm freshwater ecosystems and human health. The severity of these risks depends on event frequency, timing, location relative to sensitive waterbodies, human activities (i.e. water recreation), and interactions with stressors like climate and land use change. Those risks have an even higher impact in rural settlements with low population density, vulnerable water bodies and small-to-medium sized WWTPs. There, concentrations of discharged MPs exceed often the Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) values, which makes it necessary to introduce measures that minimize the emission of WWTPs as well as untreated sewage overflows via CSO. This study explores biochar made from recovered cellulose and biologically activated as an admixture in vertical flow CW (VFCWs) for MPs removal from

both wastewater effluent and combined sewer overflow, addressing feasibility and environmental benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of the target compounds to be monitored

The comprehensive list of compounds monitored in this study is the result of a joined agreement with the WWTP operator (Syndicat Intercommunal de Dépollution des Eaux résiduares de l'Est SIDEST in Luxembourg). The compounds were selected taking into account: a) those known to be excreted in the highest amount (in the case of pharmaceuticals: antibiotics, beta-blockers, analgesics etc), b) those known with the highest eco-toxicity (Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, PFAS), c) those known to be under observation (i.e. macrolides) or with legal obligations (i.e. isoproturon, diuron), d) those known to be especially relevant for the catchment. The list counts 28 pharmaceuticals, 9 pesticides/biocides, 13 chemicals, 3 personal care products such as fragrances and 3 sweeteners.

Selected municipal wastewater

The WWTP of Hersberg (900 People Equivalent, PE) is located in the valley of the Black Ernz, a Category VI protected area that requires tailored measures to preserve the quality of groundwater and springs. Because of that, the WWTP is equipped with a conventional activated sludge process and a CW (1200 m², 180 m³ of substrate volume, planted with reeds) treating CSO, ensuring that no untreated water is discharged into the Steebach River.

Characteristics of the substrates

Admixtures

Two biochar admixtures were produced by low-temperature pyrolysis (750 °C) from cellulose-based material. After carbonization, the biochars are mixed with minerals (such as phosphate and carbonate salts), bacteria (such as *Lactobacillus*, *Rhodopseudomonas* and *Saccharomyces*) and yeast and left to ferment at a temperature ranging between 25 and 35 °C for four weeks (so-called biological activation). The difference between the two biochars is related to the origin of cellulose:

- *plant residues for EmiSûre-AC* have been extensively studied and tested, from lab to pilot scale, under both controlled and real conditions, outperforming conventional substrates like zeolite (Venditti et al., 2024);
- *recovered cellulose from toilet paper for WOW-AC*: fine sieves in WWTPs filter cellulosic material which is then dried to 90% dry content, forming 8 mm diameter pellets. Preliminary studies (Salmeron, 2024) found that pure cellulose biochar has a low surface and micropore volume, leading to tests with 50% straw or wood mixtures to enhance the surface area.

Sand

The substrate is composed of 85 % expanded sand (Liapor, Germany) mixed with 15 % biochar produced from plant residues (Palaterra, Germany) (VFCW1 and VFCW2) and from cellulose recovered from toilet paper (VFCW3) biologically activated by fermentation.

VFCW4 is composed of 100 % lavasand (Vulkatech, Germany) as from the same composition of the existing CW present in Hersberg to treat sewage overflow.

Pilot plant design

The VFCWs consist of three 1 m³ tanks and one 300 L set up to investigate the suitability of VFCW for WWTP effluent polishing or sewage overflow treatment (Figure 1). The VFCWs are successively filled, from the bottom to the top, with a 15 cm layer of expanded clay as drainage (2-8 mm), 75 cm of packing substrate and again 10 cm of expanded clay (2-8 mm). The wetlands are planted with *Phragmites australis* + *Iris pseudacorus*. The choice of plants considers those macrophytes commonly applied to wetland configurations combining long and short routes which

are beneficial for the aeration of the entire filter bed and to improve biodiversity. The wetlands are fed simultaneously, in downflow mode. The influent is pumped at an HLR of 100 to 400 L d⁻¹m⁻² 3 times per day.

Figure 1. Schematic of the pilot plant: VFCW1 and VFCW2 (85% expanded sand, 15 % EmiSûre-AC), VFCW3 (85% expanded sand, 15 % WOW-AC), VFCW4 (100 % Lavasand)

Analytical methods

Water quality parameters

Common parameters were routinely monitored. COD, TN, PO₄-P, NH₄-N and NO₃-N were measured with Hach Lange cuvette tests while dissolved Total Carbon (DTC), Organic Carbon (DOC) and Inorganic Carbon (DIC) with a TOC analyzer (Shimadzu, B). Oxidation-reduction potential, pH and conductivity were measured with WTW (Xylem, UK) probes.

Micropollutants

MPs were analyzed by Liquid Chromatography coupled to tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). All samples were pre-concentrated by solid phase extraction before their injection. The analyses were performed externally (Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology LIST, Luxembourg) and the methodology has been previously described (Venditti, et al., 2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Occurrence of micropollutants in the catchment

Out of 56 compounds examined, 28 and 22 were detected with concentrations above the limit of quantification at least once in the WWTP influent and effluent samples, respectively.

During the conventional biological treatment, a limited number of compounds (ibuprofen, metformin, ketoprofen, naproxen, EDTA, NDA, acesulfame and cyclamate) were removed with a relative elimination exceeding 80 %, while the majority of the compounds exhibited medium (between 20 and 70 %) and low removal (below 20 %), with diclofenac and valsartan as examples respectively. This aligns with findings from other studies which report over 90 % elimination for both naproxen and ibuprofen. A zero elimination was assumed for those compounds known to be persistent and hardly removed from the conventional activated sludge treatment (i.e. carbamazepine). Compounds exhibiting relatively high concentrations (exceeding the average value of 0.5 µg L⁻¹) in the effluent samples include diclofenac, metmorfine, naproxene, benzotriazole, EDTA, NTA, galaxolide and sucralose). To comply with the guidelines established by the Luxembourgish government for the safe discharge of treated wastewater into receiving bodies, four

indicator substances defined as mandatory (carbamazepine, diclofenac, benzotriazole and clarithromycin) need to be eliminated by 80 % on average across the entire treatment process including post-treatment. Therefore, considering these results in dry weather conditions, upgrading the WWTP with a post-treatment step is considered necessary to protect the receiving water body.

Characterisation of the substrates

Both sands have a suitable Alkaline saturation (> 40 %) and buffer capacity, thus can easily provide nutrients to the reeds. Combined with high bioavailability expressed by the presence of P, K and Al, both materials have high nutrient potential which is beneficial for living bacteria and can enhance the biodegradation process.

Table 1. Summary of analysed parameters

Type of sand	Alkaline saturation (%)	CaO -> CaCO ₃ (%)	Ion/cations exchange capacity (CEC) cmol/Kg	Elemental composition		
				CAL (P,K)	CAT (Al)	Fe (%)
Expanded sand	111.3	1.82	7.39	8.4; 7.7	169.5	3.38
Lavasand	119.20	13.71	19.22	9.5; 172.9	23.6	4.69

Preliminary laboratory-scale results

Expanded sand mixed with 15 % EmiSûre-AC or WOW-AC (Venditti et al. 2024) provided high elimination for those compounds which have been found relevant in the effluent of Hersberg when small-scale tests were carried out using real WWTP effluent. Carbamazepine, diclofenac and benzotriazole were shown to be eliminated by more than 90 % allowing compliance with national regulations.

OUTLOOK

The pilot plant will be monitored over one year of operation under different conditions: both WWTP effluent and sewage overflow will be used as inlet to the CW in order to assess the performance of intensified wetlands when biochar produced in a circular economy perspective is used as admixture. Particular attention will be given to dry weather conditions with respect to receiving water body quality according to the UWWTD 2024. A comparison with the existing retention soil filter will be performed.

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